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MISOL VA MASALALARNI BIROR BELGISIGA KO'RA SINFLARGA AJRATISH BO'YICHA TOPSHIRIQLAR USTIDA ISHLASH

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada matematika darslarida o'quvchilarning kreativlik va ijodiy fikrlashlarini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari, ta'limni faollashtirish usullari, misol va masalalarni biror belgisiga ko'ra sinflarga ajratishga doir topshiriqlar turlari haqida qisqacha ma'lumot berilgan. Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida o'quvchilarning kreativ va ijodiy fikr yuritish imkoniyatlaridan foydalanishning mahsuldorligi va natijaviyligi ko'rsatilgan.

Abstract: The article provides brief information about the possibilities of developing students' creativity and creative thinking in mathematics classes, ways to activate education, examples and types of tasks for dividing problems into classes according to a certain sign. Productivity and effectiveness of using the possibilities of creative and creative thinking of students in primary grade mathematics lessons are shown.

Kalit so'zlar: topshiriq, o'quv topshirig'i, kreativ mazmunli topshiriqlar, kombinatorik masalalar, topshiriqlarni bajarishda ijodiy yondashish

Kreativ mazmundagi o'quv topshiriqlarining bir ko'rinishi bu misol va masalalarni biror belgisiga ko'ra sinflarga ajratishga doir (kombinatorik xarakterdagi) topshiriqlardir. Ularni mazmuni va tuzilishiga ko'ra quyidagi turlarga ajratish mumkin: Topshiriqlarni javobiga qarab sinflarga ajratishga; sonlar qatoridagi qonuniyatni topishga; bajarilayotgan misolda qonuniyatni topishga doir; kombinatorik topshiriqlar (1-rasm).

Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darsliklarida bunday topshiriqlar yetarlicha o'rin olgan, ammo ma'lum tizimda o'z ifodasini topmagan.

I. Topshiriqlarni javobiga qarab sinflarga ajratishga doir topshiriqlar.

1-rasm

Bunday topshiriqlar jumlasiga misol va masalalarni berilgan javoblariga qarab ularni ma'lum sinflarga ajratish; berilgan ifodalar ichidan javobi bir xil bo'lgan ifodalarni topish; ifodaga mos javoblar topib ularni chiziqlar bilan bir-biriga mos qo'yish va shunga o'xshash topshiriqlarni kiritish mumkin. I sinfda 1 dan 100 gacha bo'lgan sonlar mavzusini o'tish jarayonida quyidagi topshiriqlarni berish maqsadga muvofiq.

1-topshiriq: $8+1$; $9-2$; $2+7$; $8-2$; $6+3$; $4+3$; $5+1$; $6+1$; $8-2$. Javobi 9 chiqadigan misollarni 1-ustunga; 7 chiqadigan misollarni 2-ustunga; 6 chiqadigan misollarni 3-ustunga yozing.

2-topshiriq: 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9 sonlardan foydalanib:

a) Javobi 1 hosil bo'ladigan misollar tuzing (Masalan, $2-1=1$; $3-2=1$; ...; $9-8=1$)

b) Javobi 2 hosil bo'ladigan misollar tuzing (Masalan, $3-1=2$; $4-2=2$; ...; $9-7=2$)

b) javobi 3 hosil bo'ladigan misollar tuzing (Masalan, $4-1=3$; $5-2=3$; ...; $9-6=3$).

3-topshiriq: Quyidagi ifodalardan qiymati bir xil bo'lgan ifodalarni ajratib yozing: $7+3$; $7+4$; $5+3$; $4+4$; $8+4$; $6+4$; $9+2$; $6+5$; $9-1$; $6+2$

4-topshiriq: Ifodalar qiymatini topib, mos javoblarni chiziq bilan tutashtir.

5-topshiriq: Qiymati 8 dan kichik bo'lgan ifodalarni 1-ustunga, qiymati 8 ga teng bo'lgan ifodalarni 2-ustunga, qiymati 8 dan katta ifodalarni 3-ustunga yozing. Har bir ifoda qiymatini hisoblang:

$6+4$; $7+2$; $8-3$; $9-2$; $2+2$; $7+1$; $4+3$; $4+4$; $4+5$; $3+5$; $3+4+1$; $2+2+2$; $3+3+2$.

Ushbu topshiriqni bajarish orqali o'quvchining ko'paytirish va bo'lishga doir ko'nikmalari mustahkamlanishi bilan birga, ular tomonidan tegishli hukm, xulosa chiqarish kabi mantiqiy bilish faoliyatlari shakllanib boradi. Bu misolni yechib, o'quvchi "Har qanday songa 0 ni ko'paytirsak natija yana nol bo'ladi. 0 ni har qanday songa bo'lsak natijada yana nol hosil bo'ladi" degan xulosani chiqarsin.

Misol va masalalarni javobiga qarab sinflarga ajratishga doir topshiriqlar amaldagi boshlang'ich sinf matematika darsliklarida nihoyatda oz.

II. Sonlar qatoridagi qonuniyatni topishga doir topshiriqlar.

Bunday topshiriqlar o'quvchining mustaqil fikrlash doirasini kengaytiradi. Aqliy bilish operatsiyalari bo'lmish analiz, sintez, umumlashtirish, taqqoslash, konkretlashtirish, abstraktlashtirish kabilarni o'quvchida mujassam bo'lishga olib keladi.

Sonlar qatoridagi qonuniyatni topishga doir topshiriqlar, ko'pincha, natural sonlarni raqamlash mavzusini o'rganish va uni mustahkamlash darslarida o'rganilishi yaxshi samara

beradi. Albatta, matematika darslarida bunday topshiriqlarni ma'lum tizim asosida o'rganib borilishi o'quvchi kreativ faoliyatining tarkib topishiga xizmat qiladi.

1-topshiriq: Bir satrga bir xonali sonlarni, ikkinchi satrga ikki xonali sonlarni o'sibborish tartibida yozing.

18, 13, 2, 20, 7, 19, 11, 4, 14, 5.

Ushbu topshiriqni bajarish orqali o'quvchining bir xonali son, ikki xonali son to'g'risidagi bilimlari mustahkamlanadi. Sonlarni taqqoslash va ularni o'sish tartibida joylashtirish malakasi shakllanadi.

2-topshiriq: Quyidagi sonlar qatorida qaysi son ortiqcha?

a) 18, 17, 16, 15, 14, 7, 13, 12, 11, 10

b) 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10

Ushbu topshiriqni bajarish orqali o'quvchi sonlar ketma-ketligidagi sonlarning qandaydir qonuniyatga asoslanib joylashganini bilib olib, shu qonuniyatga bo'ysunmagan son aniqlanadi.

3-topshiriq: Bir xil raqamlardan tuzilgan barcha ikki xonali sonlarni o'sib borish tartibida yozing. Sondagi raqamlar nimani ifodalaydi?

Bir xil raqamlardan iborat ikki xonali sonlar: 11, 22, 33, 44, 55, 66, 77, 88, 99. Bu qatordagi «har bir keyingi son o'zidan oldingi sonidan 11 ta ortiq» degan qonuniyatga bo'ysunadi. Buni o'quvchi o'zi fikrlab topishi mumkin. Qatordagi har bir son bir xil raqamlardan tuzilgan. Shuning uchun birlik va o'nlik xonadagi raqamlar bir xil bo'ladi.

4-topshiriq: To'rtinchi o'nlik sonlarning eng kichigi bilan ikkinchi o'nlik sonlarning eng kattasining yig'indisi va ayirmasini toping. (40+29; 40-29).

Bunday topshiriqlarni berishdan maqsad o'quvchilarning 100 ichidagi sonlarni raqamlashga doir bilimlarini mustahkamlash va sonlar qatoridagi sonning ma'lum xossasiga ko'ra ajratib, ular ustida arifmetik amallarni bajarish ko'nikmasini tarkib toptirishdan iborat.

Isimli sonlar ishtirok etgan sonlar qatoridagi qonuniyatni topishga doir topshiriqlar o'quvchilar uchun qiziqarli.

5-topshiriq: Quyidagi ismli sonlarni ikkita qatorga shunday ajratib yozingki, har bir qatordagi son qandaydir xossaga bo'ysunsin.

12m; 4 dm 3 cm; 5 kg; 6 m 2 dm; 7 kg; 14 kg.

Bu topshiriqda o'quvchi bir ism bilan nomlanuvchi sonlarni bir qatorga, boshqa ism bilan nomlanuvchi sonlarni ikkinchi qatorga ajratib yozadi. Darhaqiqat, uzunlikni ifodalovchi ismli sonlar (12 m; 4 dm 3 sm; 6 m 2 dm) va og'irlikni ifodalovchi ismli sonlar (5 kg; 7 kg; 14 kg) alohida ajratib yoziladi.

Quyidagi topshiriq o'quvchidan ancha puxta bilim va ijodiy faoliyatni talab qiladi.

III. Bajarilayotgan misolda qonuniyatni topishga doir topshiriqlar.

Boshlang'ich sinfdanoq o'quvchilarni misol bajarish jarayonida qandaydir qonuniyatni aniqlash, umumiylikni bilish, tegishli hukm va xulosa chiqarishga o'rgatish keyingi davr ta'lim tizimida katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. O'quvchida kichik maktab davridayoq analiz, sintez, taqqoslash, konkretlashtirish, umumlashtirish kabi aqliy operatsiyalarning shakllanishi natijasida ularda mustaqil fikr yuritish ko'nikmalari tarkib topadi. Har bir topshiriqqa jiddiy yondashib, tirishqoqlik bilan bajarib, tegishli xulosalar qilishga o'rgatib borish zarur.

Bunday mazmundagi o'quv topshiriqlari bilan I sinfdan tizimli tarzda tanishtirib borish yaxshi samara beradi. Quyidagi topshiriqlar o'quvchi ijodiy faoliyatini oshirishga qaratilgan bo'lib, ularni bajarish natijasida o'quvchida maqsadga intilish, qonuniyatni aniqlash, tegishli xulosa chiqara olish kabi xislatlar tarbiyalanadi.

1-topshiriq: 1+1; 1+2; 2+2; 3+2; 3+3; 4+1; 4+2; 3+1; 4+4; 5+2. O'shishga doir bu misollardan qo'shiluvchilari bir xil sonlardan tashkil topgan misollarni ajratib olib yech. Javoblarni taqqosla.

1+1=2; 2+2=4; 3+3=6; 4+4=8. Har bir keyingi misol javobi oldingi misol javobidan 2

taga oshayapti, chunki har bir qo'shiluvchi 1 tadan oshganda yig'indi 2 taga oshadi.

2-topshiriq: 6+3; 2+6; 4+3; 5+3; 7+2; 6+4; 6+2; 6+1. O'shishga doir misollardan birinchi qo'shiluvchisi bir xil bo'lgan misollarni javoblari o'sib borish tartibida yozib oling va ularni yeching, nimani kuzatdingiz?

$$6+1=7; \quad 6+2=8; \quad 6+3=9; \quad 6+4=10.$$

Ushbu topshiriqni bajarishdan maqsad, birinchidan, o'quvchining qo'shish amali komponentlarini bilishga doir bilimni tekshirish, ikkinchidan, misollar ichidan 1-qo'shiluvchisi bir xil bo'lgan misollarni ajrata bilish ko'nikmasini aniqlash va uchinchidan eng muhimi, ajratilgan misollarning javobi o'sib borish tartibida joylashtirib "birinchi qo'shiluvchi o'zgarmas qolgan holda ikkinchi qo'shiluvchi necha birlik oshsa, yig'indi ham shuncha birlik oshadi", degan xulosa chiqara olishni aniqlashdan iborat.

3-topshiriq: 6+4; 9-4; 6+0; 7+2; 7+0; 8-3; 5+0; 3+4; 0+4 misollardan javobi qo'shiluvchilardan birortasiga teng bo'ladigan misollarning tagiga chizing. Nima uchun yig'indi qo'shiluvchiga teng bo'ladi?

Chunki dastlabki o'n ichidagi sonlar mavzusida o'quvchi "0 ni qo'shish"ni o'rganadi. O'quvchi quyidagicha xulosa qilishi mumkin: "Har qanday songa 0 ni qo'shganda yana o'sha sonning o'zi hosil bo'ladi".

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WAYS TO PREVENT DISAGREEMENTS AND SUICIDAL BEHAVIOR IN STUDENTS

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Before considering suicide as deviant behavior, let's first distinguish what deviant behavior is. The process of socialization (the process of perception by the individual of actions, social rules and values in a particular society) is characterized by the completion of a specific level of achievement of social maturity of the individual, which is characterized by the acquisition of an integral social status of the individual (a status that determines the position of a person in society). However, failures and fallacies can also occur during the social process. Due to the lack of socialization, deviant behavior appears, which is the negative forms of actions of individuals, the sphere of spiritual inferiority, principles and deviations from law and morality [2].

Sociologists call deviant behavior deviant ("deviation" in Latin-deviation). It indicates that not all actions or actions follow the rules. In some societies, only small deviations from tradition are severely punished. Everything was under control: the length of her hair, The Shape of her clothes, the order of behavior. The same was carried out by the commanders of ancient Sparta in the V century BC. At all times of society, it fought with the destruction of forms unnecessary to the life of mankind and their propagators, their removal. The methods and means of such a struggle were determined by socio-economic relations, public consciousness, interests of the ruling elite. The concept of social "evil" at all times attracted the attention of scientists. In the composition of Sociology, The "Sociology of deviant behavior" appeared, reflecting a special social theory. At the root of the sociology of deviant behavior was the French scientist, founder of the French sociological school Emile Durkheim (1858-1917). He introduced the concept of social anomie, which is based on the "state of society in which the old rules and values are not suitable for the new life and the new rules are not accepted". It is thanks to R. Merton and A. Cohen that the theory of deviant behavior was created as a separate science. Merton looked at what the social structure is motivated by the fact that some citizens of a society do not meet the action established in that society. The American sociologist A. Cohen emphasized deviant behavior as "behavior contrary to institutionally expected results" the English sociologist D. Walsh, a representative of phenomenological sociology, said that "social deviance is an additional writing status at a significant level", that is, only subjective traits. In his opinion, deviation is the result of the use of quality, social prices and sanctions, which he does not have an internal, well-known action. Such characteristics of deviant behavior do not fully reveal the objective bone affinity of its nature and antinorms. A broad understanding of the meaning of deviance is given by G.A. Avanesov: "deviant behavior should be understood as an act that does not correspond to the norms and types given in society", that is, about the violation of each social norm [1].

The struggle with deviance often gave rise to a struggle with feelings, thoughts, actions. It usually remains unproductive: over time, the fluctuations resonate, and it manifests itself very brightly. In many societies, the control of deviant behavior is not symmetrical: deviations directed to the bad side are condemned, directed to the good side, approved, accepted. Depending on the positive and negative of the deviation, several continuums of deviation can be shown. In one of its parts, the members of the group, whose deviation maximizes unacceptable behavior: revolutionaries, terrorists, atheists, traitors. In the second part, the members of the group whose deviations are perceived as the maximum: national heroes, outstanding artists, scientists, writers, children with the highest development.

Thus, all actions that lead society to disapproval and disapproval of sheep are called

deviant. This is a visible phenomenon in a wide range of areas: from ticketless travel to the murder of a person. In a broad sense, a deviant is every person who deviates from the rules or goes astray. The main forms of deviant behavior include delinquency, criminality, alcoholism, drug addiction, prostitution, and suicide.

Now let's dwell on this issue itself, which we are considering.

Suicide is a vital problem that occurs in human life as much as it lives on earth. According to researchers, suicide is an anthropological phenomenon. Compared to the phenomenon of suicide in humans and animals, this action is distinguished by intelligence. The difference between animal suicide and people is that they fall into unconscious actions. Human suicide can be seen as an element of a new civilization. As we all know, when large tribal classes began to form, suicide performed a pragmatic social function, and it also contributed to the survival of single tribes. The first known suicides in the history of mankind are the deaths of children and the elderly during periods of famine in the first class structure. According to the course of history, the methods of suicide of people have changed and become more difficult. We all know that the voluntary parting of a person from life becomes more and more over the years.

Suicide is the death of a person by thinking. Suicide is an action that occurs in all cultures. Suicidal people are usually a group of people who have suffered from spiritual distress and are in a stressful state, unable to solve their problem. They often suffer from a mental illness, especially in a depressive state for a long time, and they despair of the future. Suicide is the leading cause of death worldwide, so it is considered one of the most pressing problems in society. According to many researchers, the official statistics of suicide underestimate its true number [3].

Is suicide a more insignificant phenomenon than a global geopolitical phenomenon? And when it comes to reality, it gives a certain assessment of what is happening in society and is a phenomenon that characterizes the real appearance of this society. At the same time, the existence of extensive and comprehensive statistical data of the subject of study of suicide entrusts Western sociologists with real success. Despite this, it is also important to remember the importance of studying suicide. After all, the social dimension of the number of suicides is characterized by constant stability and increasing from the dimension of total mortality, and therefore the first place in its study is given to the general indicators of suicide-as a response to the stagnation occurring in society. Each person perceives different situations that occur in society in their own way. In this work, I conduct only on objective facts and how they influenced Kazakh society, based on the collection of data of sociologists and their analysis.

First of all, it is necessary to give a definition of suicide. This term means "an act committed with the intention of depriving oneself of life", and in the scientific literature it is used in the sense that suicide is committed consciously, thoughtfully. Death, then, considers a situation committed by a person who is unable to respond to their actions or control them as an unhappy situation, and not a situation in which the unintentional result of the subject is a suicide. What is at the heart of this suicide phenomenon? A. G. Ambrumova and many researchers consider suicide as a concept as a phenomenon of socio-psychological maladaptation of the individual. At the heart of the concept of adaptation is adaptation to living systems and the external environment, and adaptation is both a process and the result of that process. In it, the concept of maladaptation reflects the mismatch of different degrees and qualities of organisms and environments. We all know that while full identity has an impact on development, full nonconformity is the opposite of the flow of life. In the same way, the term adaptation and maladaptation is applied to systems that occupy a place between these two poles; the first of them, adds compensatory and adaptive components, and the second, describes the system from the deficient and disruptive side.

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